

DOI:**ABSTRACT**

The study assessed the conflict management among identified state universities in Region VIII during school year 2014 – 2015. A total of 130 administrators and 254 teachers from randomly sampled state Universities in Region VIII served as respondents. Most of the administrator – respondents were females, married, with a doctorate degree, have a salary range of 20 – 29k, designated as director/ manager, with 1 – 3 dependents and had been in the service for quite a long time; while the teacher respondents are females, married, with master's degree, receiving a low salary, with an academic rank of instructor, having 1 – 3 dependents and have been in the teaching service for quite a long time. There was a high level of skills of school administrators in managing conflicts between administrators and teacher, teacher and teacher, teacher and student as well as student and student as revealed by the teacher – respondents. The teachers perceived that the degree of teamwork among teachers and administrators was high. There was a significant positive relationship between the management skills and the degree of teamwork among teachers and administrators. Among other things, findings of this study underscored the need for both teachers and administrators sustain or even maximize the development of management skills in order to empower them with the skills in managing conflicts.

KEYWORDS: conflict; conflict management; management skills; school administrators.

INTRODUCTION

Conflict management is one of the most important aspects in solving most of the problems in organizations in the world today. Institutions like State Universities are not an exemption. Clear-cut policies ought to exist to provide guidance on how administrators ought to manage or resolve conflicts. People may choose to ignore them but it is hard to expect conflict to simply disappear. The school administrators as conflict managers must rise to meet the conflicts of the organizational members and always be part of the members' regular duties in conflict resolution.

Kochhar (1988) on the other hand, emphasizes the importance of administrators in managing conflicts whom he notes are the key cornerstone in the arch of school management and have the steering wheel in their hands. Kochhar asserts that the administrator should be a group leader who knows how to involve people, arrange conditions and initiate process that bring out the best in each participant, that is the school personnel who include employees (teachers, non – teaching staff), and the students.

A previous empirical study by Onsarigo (2007) had sought to determine factors influencing conflicts in institution of higher learning. The study established that, it is better to expose and resolve conflict before they damage people's relationship or even before they degenerate into violence which undermines institutional stability and performance. The study concluded that social conflicts in educational institutions demand moral authority and leadership integrity to resolve them. If not resolved, they can have a destabilizing effect on institutional performance in all learning processes. As such, the focus of this study was to determine the level of skills of the school administrators in managing conflicts. Specifically, conflict between administrator and teacher, teacher and teacher, teacher and student, student and student, and analyzed the degree of teamwork among the teachers and administrators in the identified State Universities within Eastern Visayas Region.

Bation (1989) stated that a manager needs three basic types of skills to be effective in performing managerial roles: technical skills, human skills, and conceptual skills. The manager should have the basic technical skills in order for him to perform specific kinds of activities required for his job. He must possess the ability to motivate, lead and communicate with other people to get work done through them, for he cannot perform all the work he is responsible and he must possess the skills that enable him to see the organization as a system of interacting with the environment.

Higgins (1991) stated that some people seem to be able to manage skillfully, simply as a natural outcome of their personalities, while for others, management is a skill that must be learned and developed. Unfortunately, most organizations according to Higgins, fail to recognize the need to develop skills in their managers' assuming that because they are managers, they also know how to develop.

Serious problems could be avoided if school administrators know how to handle conflicts effectively. As suggested by Pendharkar (1995), administrators shall open their communication lines to promote good employer – employee, and student – student relationships. Schools as organizations in their own right have administrators who are judged with the responsibility of maintaining their stability in order to achieve organizational goals.

The role of management in conflict is therefore, crucial for effective and efficient organization of school management. However the researcher will not overlook the fact that, the role of management in conflict is only one of the many functions, which could lead to better organization in schools. In appreciating the importance of management in education, Olembo et al. (1992) essentially provide awareness of the skills, values, and knowledge required for competent and professional management of school. In addition, the major role played by the school administrator is conflict management. Conflict which is managed well will create a conducive workplace for its employees where relationships, trusts, and respect will prevail among them. Having such a working environment will result in stimulated team spirit and increased productivity.

It is in this context that the researcher deems it necessary and timely to make this study in order to share in the challenge of effecting quality education and foster good relationship among teachers, students, and with the management. This is important because as a team they can work hand in hand to achieve the organizational goals.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to measure the conflict management skills of school administrators in State Universities of Eastern Visayas Region. In particular, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the school administrators and teachers in the identified State Universities in terms of: sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly salary, position, number of dependents, and number of years in the service?
2. What the level of skills of school administrators are as rated by teachers in managing conflicts between: administrator and teacher, teacher and teacher, teacher and student, and student against student?
3. What is the degree of teamwork among the teachers and administrators?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the management skills of the school administrators and the degree of teamwork among teachers and administrators of the state universities of Eastern Visayas Region?

Theoretical /Conceptual Framework

One basic thought that primarily relates to the rationale of this study is “Game Theory” real life is full of situations in which people intentionally or unintentionally pursue their own interests at the expense of others, leading to conflict or competition. Games used to illustrate these relationships often place the interests of two players in direct opposition; the greater the payoff for one player, the less for the other. In order to achieve a mutually productive outcome, the players must coordinate their strategies, because if each player pursues his or her greatest potential payoffs, the shared outcome is unproductive (Fisher and Keasly, 1988). From this insight, decision-makers can better assess the potential effects of their actions, and can make decisions that will more likely produce the desired goals and avoid conflict. Game theory can be used to explain and address social problems in State Universities of Region VIII. Since games often reflect or share characteristics with real situations especially competitive or cooperative situations, they can suggest strategies for dealing with such circumstances. Just as we may be able to understand the strategy of players in

a particular game, we may also be able to predict how people, political factions, or states will behave in a given situation.

In relating with the society, Fayeye (1994) asserted that the conflict perspective assumes that social behavior is best understood in terms of conflicts, or tension among competing groups. Sociologists and other social, scientists have come to see conflict not merely as a class phenomenon, but as part of everyday life in all societies. It is therefore obvious that in every culture, organization or social group, individual that form such a social unit will struggle from their respective channels to achieve one goal or the other. One person is bound to suffer, while one person will benefit, and an individual will attempt to dominate at the expense of others “competition” and conflict place confusion on people’s understanding and perception that they are taken as a similar concept. Competition usually brings out the best in people, as they strive to be top in their field. Several types of conflicts identified in the schools according to Abubakar (2005) are student-staff conflict, student-student conflict, student-principal conflict and community-school conflict. Albert (2001) stated that conflict is part of a school because teachers have varying ideas about issues, they have different backgrounds and their experiences are different. These differences can cause so much damage to the school if they are not well managed; hence the importance of conflict resolution strategies to schools administrators. School’ administrators are managers and they should be able to manage conflict effectively rather than suppress or avoid them. In managing conflicts, it is pertinent to know the causes of such conflicts and the influence it will have on the school system. Methods of resolving conflict include compromising, accommodating, collaborating, avoiding and competing (Folger, Poole and Stutman, 1997). Okorie (2002) added that the personal characteristics of a leader remain essential factors in conflict management in the school system. Age, qualification, marital status and the likes are factors that determine the extent to which a school administrator is able to achieve the school goals through effective management of conflict.. Thus, the output of this study is teamwork. Figure 1 presents the conceptual paradigm of the research.

Figure 1: Conceptual Paradigm of the study.

This research used descriptive- correlation (Gay and Air Asian, 2008) design with the questioner as its main instrument. Some items of the questionnaires were based on some related studies/ideas available in the electronic sources, books and other researches and from some experts who extended a helping hand to the researcher, thus, a dry run was conducted to suit the needs of the proposed research. The respondents of the study were composed of one hundred thirty (130) administrators and two hundred fifty four (254) teachers taken from six state universities (SUC's) in Region VIII. He selected only one school for each province in the Region because of similarities of their organizational structure. Since the population of teachers were relatively larger than the administrator respondents, a stratified random sampling was applied using the State Universities as basis for stratification. The number of teachers was the total population of teachers in the respondent State Universities, that is, more samples were taken from the State Universities with more teaching personnel. For the administrators, no sampling technique was applied but all were part of the pool of respondents. The frequency counts, percentage, item weighted means, and the use of both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the study, significance level was set at 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the study. It answers the specific questions as indicate by the results of the statistical analyses. The corresponding interpretations of the data are likewise provided in this chapter. These are presented in tables.

Table 1 Profile Of The Administrators

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Male	60	46.15
Female	70	53.85
Total	130	100.00
Marital Status		
Single	18	13.85
Married	100	76.92
Separated/ widow/er	12	9.23
Total	130	100.00
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	17	13.08
Master's Degree	52	40.00
Doctorate	61	46.92
Total:	130	100.00
Salary Range		
Less Than 70k	6	4.61
20-29k	48	36.92
30-39k	32	24.62
40-49k	23	17.69
Above 50k	21	16.15
Total	130	100.00
Designation		
Chairperson	26	20.00
Head/Sup/prin.	27	20.77
Director/Manager	32	24.62
Dean	31	23.85
IVP	14	10.77
Total:	130	100.00
Dependents		
None	36	27.69

1-3	654	50.00
4-6	20	15.38
7-9	6	6.92
10 or more	3	2.31
Total:	130	100.00
Number of years in Service		
Less than 5	7	5.38
5-10	12	9.23
11-15	13	10.00
16-20	29	22.31
21 and above	69	53.08
Total	130	100.00

The administrators were composed of 70 or 53.85 percent females and 60 or 46.15 males. The findings revealed that the educational management and the education sector in general is a woman's world. Teaching is traditionally a woman-dominated profession in the Philippines, and it's true even in State Universities.

Majority were married as shown by 100 or 76.92 percent of the respondents, while 18 or 13.85 percent supported the study of Pamplona, et al (2008) that "most of the educational managers were females and married." This revelation is contrary to the notion that once a single individual enters into the teaching profession he/she will not be able to marry. This is not true to the respondents State Universities of Region VIII.

The greatest number of the administrators have doctorate degrees with 61 or 56.92 percent, followed with master's degree, 52 or 40 percent of them and with bachelor's degree, 17 or 13.08 percent of the total. The result indicated that majority of the school administrators of the State Universities in Region VIII who were respondents of the study have masters or doctorate degrees. This implies that most, if not all, of the State Universities require a faculty member to obtain at least a master's degree before he/she could be given a designation to teach in an institution of higher learning.

As to the salary range, 48 or 36.92 percent of them belonged to the 20-29 thousand pesos salary bracket which is quite a low salary range. This means that the school administrators of State Universities in this study receive low salaries despite their heavy responsibilities corresponding to their offices. This situation is true in the government sector where the administrators receive lower salaries compared to their counterparts in the private sector. Further, the same revealed that 32 or 24.62 percent belonged to the 30-39k pesos salary range, while 23 or 11.79 percent have 40-49k pesos salary brackets which are categorized as average and high salary ranges, respectively. On the other hand, there were 21 or 16.15 percent who have salaries in the above 50k pesos bracket which is categorized as "very high." The above findings showed that in general the administrators of the State Universities of Region VIII still receive lower salaries despite their high educational qualifications.

In terms of designation, 32 or 24.62 percent were designated as Director/Manager, while 31 or 23.85 percent were designated as Deans. The findings revealed that majority of the administrators in the study were middle-level managers-administrators. On the other hand, it also revealed that there were 27 or 20.77 percent Heads/Supervisor/Principals and 26 or 20.00 percent were Chairpersons. The findings showed that there was a great number of low level managers in State Universities of Region VIII, an indication that the model of the organization is like a pyramid where the majority is in the base where they occupy the lowest position in the hierarchy. There were also 14 or 10.77 percent of the respondents who were vice-presidents of the State Universities of Region VIII.

Meanwhile, 65 or 50 percent of the respondents who have 1-3 numbers of dependents, while 36 or 27.69 percent do not have dependents. The findings indicated that most of the administrator-respondents of this study have a light burden in terms of dependency burden, since they only have a minimal number of dependents. There were also 20 or 15.38 percent of the respondents who have 4-6 dependents, while 6 or 6.92 percent of the respondents have 7-9 dependents and 3 or 2.31 percent have 10 or more dependents. These results imply that the administrator-respondents

have a relatively small family members or they may have big families but more of these members are earning and not depending on them.

Lastly, 69 or 53.08 percent of the respondents have rendered service of 21 and more years which is categorized as “long number of years in service.” The result disclosed that the administrators of the respondent – State Universities of Region VIII have been long in their service to the institution or in the government. It is a customary practice to state universities or in the government agencies in general to give promotion or designation to those who have been long years in the service. Further, 29 or 22.31 percent of the respondents have 16-20 years in service, while 13 or percent have 11-15 years in service. These result signified that the length of service is considered in giving designation, since it could be a measure of loyalty to the institution.

Table 2 Profile Of The Teacher-Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	105	41.34
Female	149	58.66
Total:	254	100.00
Marital Status		
Single	54	21.26
Married	196	77.17
Separated/widow/er	4	1.57
Total:	254	100.00
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	39	15.35
Master’s Degree	181	71.26
Doctorate	34	13.39
Total	254	100.00
Salary Range		
Less Than 70k	55	21.65
20-29k	99	38.98
30-39k	58	22.83
40-49k	37	14.57
Above 50k	5	1.97
Total	254	100.00
Academic Rank		
Instructor 1-3	96	37.80
Asst. Prof. 1-4	74	29.13
Assoc. Prof. 1-5	62	24.41
Professor 1-6	22	8.66
Total	254	100.00
Dependents		
None	75	29.53
1-3	138	54.33
4-6	39	15.35
7-9	1	0.39
10 or more	1	0.39
Total	254	100.00
Years in Service		
Less than 5	46	18.11
6-10	40	15.75
11-15	43	16.93

16-20	41	16.14
21 and more	84	33.07
Total	254	100.00

There were 149 or 58.66 percent female and 105 or 41.34 male of the total 254 respondents. This findings affirm the notion that the teaching profession is predominantly for females, as confirmed by Pamplona, et al (2008).

Most of them were married as indicated by 196 or 77.17 percent responses. The result disclosed that the teachers of the six State Universities of Region VIII were married. This finding negates the stereotyping for teachers that they will end up as old bachelors and spinsters if they will take teaching as a profession. Single respondents comprised 54 or 21.26 percent, while the separated/widower composed of 4 or 1.57 percent of the total 254 respondents. This result indicated that there were also bachelors or single ladies as well as broken marriages or widowed members of the faculty in the six selected State Universities of Region 8.

Faculty-respondents were master's degree holders as indicated by 181 or 71.26 percent of the respondents. This findings showed that six State Universities of Region VIII observed the requirement for teachers to teach in higher education institutions that they must have a master's degree. There were also 39 or 15.35 percent of the faculty who were bachelor's degree holders only while 34 or 13.39 percent of them have obtained a doctorate degree already. The results disclosed that there were still teachers who need to earn higher degrees, while others have obtained the highest degree possible. This implies that the faculty of the State Universities is a strong area or force since it is composed highly qualified manpower.

A great number of 99 or 38.98 percent belong to the 20-29 thousand pesos bracket, while 58 or 22.83 percent have 30-39 thousand pesos salary. These findings revealed that most of the faculty-respondents in the identified State Universities of Region 8 belong to low or average salary ranges. This implies that the teachers of state universities need to increase their salaries in order to elevate their economic status.

Majority of them were instructors as disclosed by 96 or 37.50 percent, while 74 or 29.13 percent were Assistant Professors, 62 or 24.41 percent were Associate Professor and 22 or 8.66 percent were Full Professors. The results indicated that most of the faculty-respondents of the six State Universities were in still the lower academic ranks, and only few were in the higher academic ranks. This finding is understandable since there are many requirements to satisfy before a faculty member could be promoted into the higher ranks.

The biggest number of 138 or 54.33 percent has 1-3 dependents. The findings disclosed that majority of the faculty respondents have a light dependency burden. On the other hand, there were 75 or 29.53 percent have no dependents, while 39 or 15.35 percent have 4-6 dependents. Only one or .39 of the teachers have 7-9 and 10 or more dependents, respectively. The teachers of the State Universities of Region VIII have a relatively middle-sized family with 3 dependents, a scenario that is true to the entire country.

A great number of 84 or 33.07 percent of the respondents have 21 or more years in the service which is considered very long. This findings implies that most of the teachers in respondent State Universities of Region VIII were loyal to their institutions that they can stay for a long time. There were also 46 or 18.11 percent have 11-15 years of service in the University. Similarly, there were 41 or 16.14 percent and 40 or 15.75 percent have 6-10 years service. These results signified that the faculty-respondents of the identified State Universities have varied number of years in service in their respective Universities.

Table 3 Summary Of Perceptions By The Teacher – Respondents On The Skills Of Administrators In Managing Conflicts

State University	Administrator and Teacher		Teacher and Teacher		Teacher and Student		Student to Student		Grand Mean	
	Mean	Responses	Mean	Responses	Mean	Responses	Mean	Responses	Mean	Responses
ESSU	3.58	High	3.56	High	3.63	High	3.67	High	3.61	High
LNU	3.37	Average	4.52	Very High	4.54	Very High	4.71	Very High	4.28	High
NSU	3.66	High	3.83	High	3.95	High	4.03	High	3.87	High
SLSU	3.77	Average	4.16	High	4.25	High	4.24	High	4.10	High
SSU	3.79	High	4.39	High	4.48	High	4.47	High	4.28	High
UEP	4.65	Very High	4.91	Very High	4.58	Very High	4.92	Very High	4.76	Very High
Grand Mean	3.80	High	4.23	High	4.24	High	4.34	High	4.15	High

Managing Conflicts between Teacher and Administrator. The overall mean obtained was 3.74, interpreted as “high”. This finding disclosed that the teachers perceived that their administrators have a high level of skills in managing conflicts between the administrators and faculty members. The result implies that teachers were satisfied and contented with what their administrators are doing in terms of resolving their conflicts.

Managing Conflicts between Teacher and Teacher. The findings disclosed that the teachers rated their administrators to have a high level of skills in managing conflicts between teacher and teacher. It implies that the teachers of the six State Universities in Region VIII have high regard to their respective administrators in resolving conflicts between and among their teachers.

Managing Conflicts between Teacher and Student. It is revealed that the overall mean score in all items and universities is 4.29 interpreted as “High,” with all items rated as “High.” The findings disclosed that the way the administrators of the State Universities involved in this study deal with the conflicts between teachers and student was perceived to be high. This means that the administrators have a high level of skills in resolving conflicts that arise between the teachers and students as perceived by the teachers in the six identified State Universities of Region VIII.

Managing Conflicts Between Student and Student. It was found out that the administrators have a “High” level of skills in managing conflicts between student to student as indicated by the overall mean from six universities and the 15 items rated by the respondents was 4.34. This result signified that the faculty-respondents of the identified state universities of Region VIII perceived that their administrators are doing very well in dealing with conflicts between and among students in their respective universities. It implies that the administrators can manage conflicting situations. All the items were rated by the faculty respondents with “High” level of skills as dealt by their respective administrators. The findings imply that the different universities are having uniqueness in terms of how their administrators deal with conflicts especially with regards to resolving conflicts between student to student.

Table 4 Degree Of Teamwork Among Teachers And Administrators As Perceived By The Teachers In Selected State Universities Of Region VIII

Items	Mean	Responses
1. We try to set procedures or protocols to ensure that things are orderly and run smoothly (e.g. minimize interruptions; everyone gets the opportunity to have their say).	4.06	High
2. We are quick to get on with the task on hand and do not spend too much time in planning stage.	3.90	High
3. Our team feels that we are all in it together and shares responsibilities for the team's success or failure.	3.93	High
4. We have thorough procedures for agreeing on our objectives and planning the way we will perform our tasks.	3.98	High
5. Team members are afraid or do not like to ask others for help.	3.87	High
6. We take our team's goals and objectives literally, and assume a shared understanding.	3.96	High
7. The team leader tries to keep order and contributes to the tasks at hand.	3.94	High
8. We do not have fixed procedures we make them up as the tasks or project progresses.	3.88	High
9. We generate lots of ideals, but we do not use many because we fail to listen to them and reject them without fully understanding them.	3.86	High
10. Team members do not fully trust the other members and closely monitor others who are working on a specific task.	3.93	High
11. The team leader ensures that we follow the procedures, do not argue, do not interrupt, and keep to the point.	3.97	High
12. We enjoy working together; we have a fun and productive time.	4.02	High
13. We have accepted each other as members of the team.	4.10	High
14. The team leader is democratic and collaborative.	3.39	High
15. We are trying to define the goal and what tasks need to be accomplished.	4.09	High
16. Many of the team Members have their own ideas about the process and personal agendas are rampant.	3.95	High
17. We fully accept each other's strength and weakness.	4.06	High
18. We assign specific roles to team members (team leader, facilitator, time keeper, note taker, etc.)	4.07	High
19. We try to achieve harmony by avoiding conflict.	4.11	High
20. The tasks are very difficult from what we imagined and seem very difficult to accomplish.	4.03	High
21. There are many abstract discussions of the concepts and issues, which make some members impatience with these discussions.	4.07	High
22. We are able to work through group problems.	3.98	High
23. We argue a lot even though we agree on the real issues.	3.85	High
24. The team is often tempted to go above the original scope of the project.	3.87	High
25. We express criticism of others constructively.	3.87	High
26. There is a close attachment to the team.	3.84	High
27. It seems as if little is being accomplished with the project's goals.	3.84	High
28. The goals we have established seem unrealistic.	3.76	High
29. Although we are not fully sure of the project's goals and issues, we are excited and proud to be on the team.	3.75	High

30. We often share personal problems with each other.	3.88	High
31. There is a lot of resisting of the task on the hand and quality improvement approaches.	3.90	High
32. We get a lot of work done.	4.10	High
Overall	3.96	High

There was a “High” degree of teamwork/cohesiveness among teachers and administrators in resolving conflicts in the six state universities of Region VIII. The rest of the items were perceived by the teacher – respondents to be “High” as indicated by the item means ranging from 4.10 to 3.75. The findings mean that there is a high degree of teamwork among teachers and administrators in state universities of Region VIII which would result to less number of conflicts. It implies that if there is a high level of teamwork among teachers and administrators in state universities of Region VIII, there would be lesser conflicts and would result to higher level of performance of the teachers, administrators, and the university.

Table 5 Relationship Between Administrators’ Management Skills And The Extent Of Teamwork

Variables	Administrator and Teacher		Teacher and Teacher		Teacher and Student		Student and Student	
	r value	Interpretation	r value	Interpretation	r value	Interpretation	r value	Interpretation
Extent of teamwork	0.551	Significant*	0.606	Significant*	0.578	Significant*	0.621	Significant*

* Level of Significance at 0.01

** Level of Significance at 0.05

On the relationship between the level of management skills and the extent of teamwork among teachers and administrators of state universities in Region VIII, the obtained r – value was higher than the p – value at .01 level of significance. This finding disclosed that there was a significant relationship between the level of management skill of the administrators in managing conflicts to the extent of teamwork among teachers and administrators. This means that the higher level of management skills of the administrators in managing conflicts the better would be the teamwork of the teachers and administrators in state universities. This implies that when there is a strong bonding or teamwork in the organization, there would be less conflicts that would occur, and when the administrators could address well the conflicts that arise in their organization, the better would be the relationship among the members of the organization. With the above findings, the null hypothesis in this study was rejected.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based from the findings revealed in the study, several conclusions were formulated: First, the administrator-respondents were mostly female, married, with doctorate degrees, having a low salary of 20-29 thousand pesos, designated as Director/manager in their universities, with 1-3 dependents and very long years of experience in the service, i.e. 21 years and above. On the other hand, majority of the teacher-respondents were females, married, have master’s degree, with 20-29 thousand pesos salary range, mostly instructors, having 1-3 dependents and very long in the service of 21 years and above. Second, the level of management skills of the administrators in the six identified state universities of Region 8 was “High” in managing conflicts between administrator and teacher, teacher and teacher, teacher and student as well as student to student. Third, there was a “High” degree of Teamwork among teachers and administrators as perceived by the teacher-respondents in the six identified State Universities in Region VIII as perceived by the teacher-respondents. Lastly, a significant relationship existed between the management skills and the degree of teamwork among teachers and administrators in the six identified State Universities as perceived by the teacher-respondents. The study recommends that although it was revealed in this study that the management skills of the administrators in the six identified State Universities in Eastern Visayas Region were “High”, it is still suggested that concrete measures should be made to maintain this or even increase it to the highest level. Management skills of the administrators be honed properly to prepare them for any conflict that would occur in their respective universities. This could be done through attendance in trainings and seminars especially designed for the said purpose.

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